

Paper 3

INNOVATIONS AND BEST PRACTICES IN DESIGNING QUALITY CURRICULAR ASPECTS FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Curriculum is an essential ingredient of any higher education system regardless of what the education level is. All other aspects whether teaching, learning and evaluation or research and development, infrastructure and learning resources, student activities and support system revolve around it. Therefore, curricular aspects and the best practices connected to curriculum design and development play a very significant dimension of the quality of higher education since the curriculum has a decisive role in steering the other elements of quality. Reviewing and updating of the curriculum is the essential ingredient of any vibrant academic system. There ought to be a dynamic curriculum with necessary additions and changes introduced in it from time to time by the respective university with a prime objective to maintain updated curriculum and also providing their inputs to take care of fast paced development in the knowledge of the subject concerned. Designing of the curriculum to suit the clientele is important. Revising the curriculum should be a continuous process to provide an updated education to the students at large. Leaving a few, there have been many universities where this exercise has not been done for years together and it is not uncommon to find universities maintaining, practicing and teaching still on the curriculum as old as few years or even more than a decade. In order to overcome these lacunae NAAC has made efforts to compile the best practices in each of the criterion of quality and disseminate the same through publications, seminars, workshops and conferences across the country. This paper is an attempt to identify some of the best practices in curriculum design and enhance the quality of higher education in India

Key Words: Curriculum design, higher education. Innovation, Best practices, Quality Education

Introduction

Higher education contributes to the promotion of the development of abilities and skills cognitive, affective and psychomotor domain. It contributes to the promotion of civic behavior, nation building and social cohesion through the transmission of democratic values and cultural norms. This supports the formation and strengthening of social capital, generally understood as the benefits of membership in a social network that can provide access to resources, guarantee accountability and serve as a safety net in terms of crisis.

The institutions, relationships and norms that emerge from higher education are instrumental in influence in the quality of society's interactions, which underpin economic, political and social development.

Higher education has many purposes:

1. Acquisition of concrete knowledge and skills.
2. Developing the ability to reason systematically about critical questions and issues.
3. To place facts in a broader context.
4. To consider the moral implications of actions and choices.
5. To communicate knowledge and questions effectively.
6. To nurture habits that promotes lifelong learning behaviors outside the formal settings.
7. Developing the skills of analysis synthesis and argumentation.

In a changing context, the needs and aspirations of the students have to be met through the curriculum and curriculum transactions. The educationists and academicians need to take stock of the present scenario and introspect to transform the educational institutions to meet the present day challenges. The institutions of higher education need to have a clear understanding of what they are seeking to achieve through their curricular offerings, research and extension programmes.

In today's complex and competitive academic environment in higher education, professional approaches and best practices alone can act as catalysts for quality improvements in the system as a whole. The quality of curriculum and the human infrastructure would make a quantum difference in the quality of graduates, which is the outcome of such inputs. It will exert significant influence on the international reputation of the Indian higher education system in general.

OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY

- To identify best curriculum activities initiated by institutes of repute.
- To study the advantages and drawbacks of these curriculum initiatives.

This study is based on the secondary data. It is a compilation of various good practices in curriculum designing followed by colleges of good repute.

Discussion

CHOICE BASED CREDIT SYSTEM

Realizing that the present system offers a very rigid pattern, which is inadequate to satisfy the interests and aspirations of the students, it was necessary for the university to move with the times and offer programmes to cater to the diverse needs of the students according to their learning ability and pace of learning. Optimization of resource use to achieve the best realization and nurture of talents among the large student community prompted the university to initiate this curricular reform[1].

The Objectives

- To develop the curriculum with student focus
- To promote academic excellence in the areas of student choice
- To provide adequate flexibility in the choice of subjects to the students
- To make the system more self-reliant by introducing at least partially the internal assessment process

Under the design of 'Choice Based Credit System (CBCS)' the curriculum has been molded into a three-tier structure.

Hard Core papers - These are papers that the parent department decides as compulsory components for the learners aspiring for a degree in that discipline.

Soft Core Papers - These are papers allied to the learners. They are inter-disciplinary and application oriented. Learners are given options to choose from a list of Soft Core papers provided by both parent as well as other departments.

Optional Papers - These are papers the learners opt to choose according to their own preference from the main discipline as well as from other departments[2].

Courses like Value Education, Women Studies, and Personality Development are incorporated in the curriculum for the holistic development of all the learners. In addition to these, there is a unique feature "Prospective Course" available for the Under Graduate learners.

CERTIFICATE COURSE

The objective in introducing Certificate Courses was to provide all students an opportunity to move across streams and take up courses of their interest or specialized courses in their chosen core subjects. Specifically, it aims to develop:

More in depth knowledge of their subject

Skills and a broader overview in other areas of their interest

Help them to grow (w) holistically[3].

CURRICULUM RESTRUCTURING FOR ENHANCED CAREER OPPORTUNITIES

An educational endeavor to be purposeful must lead to the ultimate goals and aspirations of the graduates. This is most relevant in the Indian scenario where millions of students graduate without adequate competence to meet the demands of the present socio-economic and technological environment. Industry finds more than 40% of the graduates employable. From a survey of the stakeholders and prospective employers, it was realized that graduates are not found suitable for the opportunities the various organizations are seeking for[4]. The feedback from the stakeholders clearly indicated the need to enhance the employability of graduates. They enter the higher education institutions with lots of aspirations for building a career for them to be financially independent and professionally competent. The field of education is currently undergoing a paradigm shift with the onus now being on the learner, which means students have to be motivated for taking initiative with the stimulated environment created by the curriculum and the way it is transacted and the academic ambience provided to them. The employers expect from the graduates to make value addition to the organization in terms of knowledge, skills and competencies for problem solving. Improving the quality in all respects to increase the productivity of the organization is significant for any organization. The quality of the graduate has to be important in this context to achieve the end result. This can only happen with reforms in the curriculum to make it socially, economically and technologically relevant[5].

The Objectives

The college has a uniquely conceived mission to provide a unique learning experience which will enable the students to realize their innate potential and mould their overall personality ably supported by 4 mission goals:

- Promoting academic excellence
- Developing self reliant individuals
- Providing career opportunities and
- Creating socially responsible citizen

THE INTEGRATED PEDAGOGICAL MODEL followed the pattern of a Typical Model. The Model is based on the assumptions: 1) Every individual's learning depends on his/her context, 2) An individual can be made to contemplate and reflect on experiences, 3) Reflecting on Experiences lead to more responsible action, 4) Evaluation of the process and product of learning leads to further refinement of the teaching-learning process. NAAC for Quality and Excellence in Higher Education[6]

Phase 1 Context: In this phase, the teacher analyzes the context of the learner as well as the subject. With respect to the context of the learner the teacher does a thorough study of the following: a) Predispositions and mindset, b) Readiness levels, c) Entry Behavior, d) World of the learner (family, socio-economics, psychological school of environment), e) Learning Styles, f) Natural talents. With respect to the subject the analysis includes the following: i) Advance Organizers and Unit Analysis, ii) Instructions Objectives and Specifications, iii Behavioural Objectives and Specifications, iv) Methodology to be used for the Lesson, v) Methodology to be used for the Evaluation, vi) Teaching Aids to be used, vii) Resources and References[7][8].

Phase 2 Experience: The term Experience is used to describe an activity in which, in addition to a cognitive grasp of the matter being considered, some sensation of an affective nature is registered by the student. In this phase, the teacher provides learning experiences based on the analysis on Context. It means "testing knowledge internally". Here, concepts, relationships and generalizations are dealt with, through the use of imagination and feelings. Through questioning, imagining, investigating and analyzing, students construct and organize data into a whole. Experiences provided may be either direct or vicarious. During this phase, learning is made challenging and experiential

Phase 3 Reflection: At this level, the memory, the understanding, the imagination and the feeling are used to capture the meaning and the essential value of what is being captured. The essential value of what is being studied, to discover relationship with other aspects of knowledge and human activity, and to appreciate its implications in the ongoing search for truth and freedom. This is a formative and liberating process. It forms the conscience of learners (their beliefs, values, attitudes and their entire way of thinking) in such a manner that they are led to move beyond knowing, to undertaking action. This is done through inquiry and not indoctrination[9][10].

Phase 4 Action: In this phase, the learner considers the experience from a personal human point of view and makes choice that are internalized and then manifested externally. Based on the learning that has happened, the students are stimulated to action that proceeds from global to local[11][12].

Phase 5 Evaluation: In this phase, the degree of knowledge mastery, the competence level and the behavioral changes are assessed[13][14].

CONCLUSION

NAAC has a mandate for not only assessing and accrediting higher education institutions, but also enabling institutions to understand their quality gaps and to help in enhancing their quality status. In the process, it has identified best practices of some institutions, which has made an impact on the quality of education they impart. NAAC has been advocating best practices to be internalized by institutions through seminars, conferences and workshops and also through the establishment of Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC). This is an attempt to compile best practices in terms of curriculum aspects which is the first criteria in NAAC certification.

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